

FORMS OF ORGANIZING PHYSICAL ACTIVITIES WITH CHILDREN OF PRIMARY AND SCHOOL AGE AND WAYS OF THEIR IMPLEMENTATION

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Annotation. This article discusses aspects of achieving results in the process of revealing the organizational and pedagogical foundations for achieving high efficiency in the physical education of students of a higher educational institution. At the same time, the results obtained during the study are presented.

Keywords: physical culture, physical education, physical qualities, physical exercises, means, method

The state form of Organization of physical education is mandatory for all children attending preschool educational organizations. Physical education classes in these institutions are carried out in accordance with the educational and educational program in the preschool educational organization, in which the tasks, content and forms of Organization of physical exercises are determined. The program provides for the gradual assimilation by children of specific motor skills, skills and knowledge. The program of each age group mainly provides new teaching materials; the physical exercises and games studied are systematically repeated and strengthened.

Physical education classes are conducted by Physical Educators. Classes are mandatory for all healthy children. Independent forms of Organization of physical education are carried out by parents in the family.

Purpose of the study: as mentioned above, the effectiveness of solving the problems of the targeted use of factors of Physical Culture in the early and preschool age depends on the organization of the appropriate mode of action. It is based on daily physical exercises and games of various forms under the guidance of an educator (in preschool educational organizations), in the process of independent play activities of parents (family) and children.

Forms of physical exercise are understood as ways of organizing the educational process, each of which is characterized by a certain type of relationship (interaction) between the educator and educators, as well as the corresponding conditions of training [1].

In officially organized physical education practice and independent physical education, various forms of training have developed: for example, in educational organizations, competitive forms of Organization of physical education and sports activities characteristic of

physical education classes, various forms of independent physical education classes, small forms of physical exercises (in particular, specific regular forms of physical education, such as breaks and minutes of physical Of course, they are not the same in terms of their place and importance in the general system of physical education.

The main ones include relatively large forms of systematically structured training, since effective training in these means of movement is necessary for sufficient mass development and support of the functional characteristics of the organism, its physical qualities and related abilities. This includes, first of all, lesson forms of training. At the same time, at different stages of the process of long-term physical education, depending on specific conditions and Main Stage tasks, other forms of basic training are used, including ordered forms of independent training, competitive forms of Organization of sports training, etc.

In the optimal organization of the process of physical education in combination with the main forms, additional forms of physical exercise, including small forms included in the general lifestyle and subordinate to the main activity (elementary Gymnastics, physical education n breaks, physical education minutes, etc.), active rest, full recovery, forms of collective and individual organization of movement activity as a factor of healthy

It is certainly no coincidence that such a variety of forms of training appeared in the practice of physical education. This expands the possibilities of rational organization of the training system, which is applied to their specific orientation and Real conditions, taking into account the specifics of the contingent of students, their group and individual characteristics, allows you to give the necessary flexibility to the organization of classes, to ensure compliance with the form of training. However, it is important that with different forms of training, their structure has certain common features. They are, of course, more fully expressed in the main forms of training.

Physical education of the specified type is the main form of work with children in preschool educational organizations. It is recommended to conduct physical education classes 2 times a week (for 10-20 minutes) with children of early preschool age (1-4 years). In the group of older children (5-7 years old), physical education classes are held 3 times a week in the morning hours for 30-40 minutes (excluding daily morning hygienic Gymnastics) [2].

Physical education classes with children in preschool educational organizations differ in their structure, content and methods of conducting.

Children should be in physical education uniform (clothing) during classes: in T-shirts and shorts, in sports shoes. Adults should also be in sportswear. Thorough preparation for training, the establishment of specific tasks, the structure of the training plan, guides and large inventory should be selected in advance, etc.k.

Research materials and techniques: the educator prepares large and small sports equipment before the start of training and places it in a specific place. On the instructions of the educator, children independently take flags, sticks, cubes and put them in place at the end of the exercise.

The structure of physical education classes is general and consists of three parts:

- preparation (18% of the total training time);
- basic (67% of total training time);
- final (15% of the total training time).

Such a distribution of training corresponds to the capabilities of children and ensures an increase in physical activity during training and its decrease by the end of training [1].

The purpose of the preparatory part is to bring the child's body to the main load, focusing on further work. In the first part of the workout, exercises for walking, running, banding, re-lined up, simple game tasks are offered. The educator should pay special attention to the alternation of exercises in walking and running: their uniformity makes children tired, reduces the quality of exercise, and can also lead to undesirable consequences (violation of posture, straightening of the leg, etc.).

The main part of the training includes exercises of the longest and general developmental nature, the main types of movements, action games. At the same time, it is important to perform all kinds of exercises for the developing body of the child. This part is characterized by the greatest physical activity.

General developmental exercises have a direct effect on the body as a whole, individual muscle groups and joints, and also help to improve coordination of movements, orientation in space, have a positive effect on the cardiovascular and respiratory systems of the body.

To correctly perform general developmental exercises, various initial poses are used: standing, sitting, kneeling, lying on the back and abdomen. By changing the starting pose, the educator can complicate or facilitate the Action Task.

General developmental exercises with subjects remind children of games. They will be happy to play with a rattle, a ball, a flag, a doll. Imitation exercises ("chickens", "sparrows", etc.) are also used in exercises with subjects.

The educator plans training, depending on which equipment is used in it; for example, in exercises with sticks, flags, it is recommended to line up in rows at a sufficient distance from each other, since lined up in rows does not allow you to achieve the desired range of motion and, moreover, can lead to injuries.

In the main part of the training, you can use high-action games, including, if possible, movements performed by all children at the same time (running, jumping, throwing, crawling, etc. for example: "airplanes", "mother chickens and chicks", "Sun and rain", "horses", etc.) are used.

The third and last part of the workout is small in size, which includes games and low-intensity play exercises that help gradually decrease movement activity. It uses walking exercises, simple game tasks. It provides the child with a gradual transition from an excited state to a relatively calm one, giving him the opportunity to switch to another activity.

Systematic, gradual and gradual increase in physical load has a positive effect on the general development of the child and helps to improve his motor skills. At first, as a rule, children perform new movements incorrectly, with excessive tension. Therefore, it is necessary to make minimum requirements for them.

The power of assimilation of exercises and basic movements depends on the mandatory repetition of the passed.

Repetition should not be mechanical and monotonous, since interest in movement activity is lost. Therefore, at the first stage of teaching children, when repeating the material, it is necessary to use various guides, changing the situation without changing the nature of the actions.

The educator's speech during training should be calm and expressive in order to attract the attention and interest of children. Referring to the child by his name during the game, timely assistance and stimulation will attract the child and increase the child's desire to perform the action independently.

According to the content and methods of training, they can be game, story and mixed.

Game classes differ in that action games with appropriate actions are selected to solve problems. This type of training includes familiar actions, the task of which is to combine physical actions in changing situations, develop physical qualities and motor skills.

Story Lessons increase children's interest in action. Story lessons on Physical Culture also consist of three parts: preparatory, basic and final.

The preparatory part increases the emotional state of children, activates their attention, prepares the body for the upcoming physical load. In this part of the training, game motivation is created and a game task is set. But in some classes, the motivation of game-based movement activity is transferred to the beginning of the main part, and the involvement of children in the performance of exercises is indirect: musical accompaniment (co-authorship), the sound of tanbur reminds of familiar exercises, etc.

In the main part of the training, children form the skills of performing movements, learn and strengthen them, develop physical qualities and motor skills. This part of the plot is characterized by an increased saturation of the plot.

In the final part of the training, the developed muscle activity is gradually transferred to a calm state, children continue to communicate with Game signs, children adapt to independent play.

Mixed training consists of gymnastic exercises (direct, general developmental exercises, basic movements) and action games. Gymnastic exercises with preschool children are held in the form of game exercises.

From time to time, it is useful for the educator to conduct Control classes. The level of motor skills and physical qualities of children is checked, their inclinations and interests are determined. In different types of training, the number of parts and their sequence remains unchanged, which does not depend on the content of training (gymnastics and sports exercises used, games with movements).

As mentioned above, as mass physical education movements develop, different forms of physical exercise appear and increase in different areas. A sufficiently developed typology of the set of all existing forms of Organization of physical education classes has not yet been created, which is especially explained by their diversity and dynamic renewal to some extent at the moment.

Typical signs that distinguish small forms of exercise from large ones are mainly the following:

- a relatively narrow area of activity. Within the framework of small forms, as a rule, certain tasks are solved, the implementation of which objectively does not guarantee a sharp shift in the state of those involved, but to some extent can contribute to it. These tasks are as follows: to accelerate the development of the body in a moderate tone (tone) during the transition from a state of rest to daily activity (as seen in morning hygienic exercise sessions); optimization of the dynamics of operational efficiency and Prevention of its negative impact on the state of the body (such as the use of positive effects of outdoor activities within the framework of physical education breaks, physical education minutes), maintaining certain aspects of acquired physical fitness and creating certain conditions that contribute to the effectiveness of basic training (for example, when performing;
- relatively short duration. Small forms of banding training, they are short-term training or a series of physical exercises that often last a few minutes;

- a slight differentiation of the structure. In small forms, the structure (content) is as if broken: the preparatory, basic and final parts of the training are not only short-term, but also limited in content and are practically not expressed in certain situations;
- relatively low level of functional loads.

From all this, in essence, the additional role of small forms of training in the general system of physical education arises. The methodology for organizing small forms of training, of course, does not depend on the level of training of students, their age, individual and other characteristics, as well as external conditions. Most importantly, its specificity is associated with the specific direction of training and the role of the individual in the general way of life.

To discern the above points, below are examples of small forms of training that are used in the physical education of children of the early and preschool age:

- morning hygienic Gymnastics;
- physical fitness breaks and physical education minutes.

Morning hygienic Gymnastics (Egg) is aimed at activating the activity of the body, increasing its effectiveness and forming the correct posture. Morning Gymnastics improves the functioning of the cardiovascular, nervous and respiratory systems, increases metabolism, strengthens and develops muscles, improves mood and work, helps to get in good shape. Morning exercises strengthen health by activating the activity of all organs and systems.

Egg tools include simple general development exercises in combination with water procedures, rubbing, tempering. Its duration is 5 minutes for children from 2 to 4 years old (3-4 exercises of a playful and imitation character), 6-8 minutes-for children 4-5 years old, 8-10 minutes – for children 6 years old. The structure of morning gymnastics can be as follows: walking, running, exercises for the muscles of the arm and shoulder girdle, exercises for the torso (back and abdomen), exercises for the legs, short-term jogging and walking for the purpose of recovery. In order for the complex of morning Gymnastics exercises not to bore the child, it is necessary to periodically, after about 7-10 days, alternate exercises 1-2[1].

When organizing morning hygienic gymnastics with preschool children, the following methodological rules must be observed (Table 9).

Table 9. Methods of performing morning hygienic gymnastics with students of a preschool educational institution

Age Duration,	Age Duration,	Age Duration,	Age Duration,	Age Duration,
3-4	6	4-5	5-6 times	- - exercises for the arch muscles of the arms;
4-5	8	5-6	6-7 times	- - exercises for the muscles of the torso;
5-6	10	6-8	7-8 times	- - exercises for the arch muscles of the legs;
6-7	12	8-12	8-10 times	- - exercises in a sitting and lying position; - - jump
Structure and content of morning hygienic Gymnastics				
Training sessions content	Training sessions content	Training sessions content	Training sessions content	Training sessions content
Prep	1. Development 2. Different types of walking 3. Step-by-step transition to running. Running. Walking. Breathing exercises 4. Lined up (in a circle, in a group, in a trio, in a row, etc.).			Monitoring the situation
Basic	5. A complex of general developmental			exercises external switch complexes: in place and in motion without objects; with subjects with small balls, with a medical ball, with a harpoon, with a gymnastic stick, etc.; using a gymnastic bench, on the Swedish wall grid; in a pair, etc.

Closing 6.	6. Walking	
Taxlil parameters of morning hygienic Gymnastics		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization of children • Space for morning exercises • Compliance with hygiene requirements: • Cleaning and ventilation of the Hall (ventilation) • Temperature indicators • Comfort of children's clothes and shoes • Duration 		
Components:		
1) Introduction part	2) main part	2) closing part
* Group exercises in turn	* quantity	* breath recovery
* State formation	* norm	
* Foot formation	* sequence	
* Dance moves	* age-appropriate	
Quality of educator instructions	Quality of exercises performed by children (individual work)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • * knowledge of terminology • * clarity of commands • * elements of creativity • * maintain children's interest and attention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • * status management • * rhythmicity to music • * equipment use • * level of movement activity of children 	

It is necessary to raise children accustomed to doing morning exercises, pay special attention to those who do not want to get out of bed and wake up sluggish in the morning. When organizing classes, it is first used to perform 5-6 imitation (imitation) movements: 1 exercise for the arms and shoulder girdle, 2-3 exercises for the body, then for the legs – sitting, jumping or running exercises. They finish gymnastics with a slow, calm walk.

As a result of the systematic conduct of games and their correct Management, children can develop the most important volitional qualities: endurance, discipline, the ability to regulate their own behavior.

Academician I.P.Pavlov found that there are two processes in the cerebral hemisphere: excitation and braking. The younger the child, the more excitation prevails than braking. When systematically conducting games that require endurance, braking, children begin to

gain stamina, self-control when they stop breaking the rules, and develop braking processes in them.

P.F. Lesgaft wrote: "play is an exercise that prepares the child for life. Games are the most useful activity for the child, through which he gets used to the movements that form its basis, and these activities are usually associated with a feeling of uplifting pleasure". But only with the guidance of the educator can the game have a positive effect on the child. Therefore, the educator must know the educational tasks, age characteristics in each group, the content of the games and the methodology for conducting them [3].

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